

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ROLE OF SPORTS AND GAMES IN THE SYSTEM OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In the article physical education of sports games in the system place and importance about word done _ Sports games features , sportc from sports games in training of practitioners health improve duties solution to do and to them sports propaganda their work take to go issues cover received*

Key words: *physical education, sports, sports games, physical exercises, action games, physical activity, tool.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ РОЛИ СПОРТА И ИГР В СИСТЕМЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В статье физкультура спортивных игр в системе место и значение слова сделано _ Особенности спортивных игр , виды спорта от спортивных игр в тренировке физкультурников решение задач по улучшению здоровья занимающихся и к ним спортивная пропаганда освещаются вопросы их работы. полученный*

Ключевые слова: *физическое воспитание, спорт, спортивные игры, физические упражнения, подвижные игры, двигательная активность, инструмент.*

Human perfect development of sports games in assistance efficiency , first of all , their to himself special characteristics , secondly , their participation which of people to the body deep different effect , physical adjectives development and vital tool skills development with explained ; thirdly , different age people for readiness and readiness (physical activity level wide scale in order put - unimportant , to health directed from training the most high level sports level physical and spiritual to stress) ; fourth , emotional charge with , this on the ground everyone equal - "both old and young " ; fifth , sports games are unique landscape , therefore for them other sports _ with comparing it won't be . At school initial sports games in classes elements physical education in their classes open the games teaching in the process is studied . Sports games straight away learning starts from the 5th grade .

Physical education 3 games per program includes - basketball , football , hand ball , of them one optional is studied . The eighth from class starting from to the program volleyball is also included . Sports games common and professional education in institutions physical education in the field wide demonstration done _ Study in their work this basketball , volleyball , hand ball , soccer , from school except in work , physical education , sports and recreation while above telling of the passed except table tennis , badminton and others is taught . Sports games almost all sports _ according to athletes common physical preparation , physical qualities development and motor experience of athletes in enrichment efficient tool as wide is used . Sports games main features from that is external _ from the games different as they are not only of muscles main groups , maybe in general man for necessary has been another many qualities , for example , agility , endurance , speed skill and physical strength they develop . Har a sports game known of indicators work improves . Physical of virtues besides , physical didn't happen qualities logic exists _ to the situation fast relationship development contribution adds , that is

briefly in other words , a person mental develops . port games non-standard or to the situation about physical are exercises . This exercises "motor movements in execution structure , direction and strength in advance unplanned , but sports activities different at the points surface coming to situations with the connection is described . Engine duties own on time and right solution to do nerve system extrapolation to do , from sensitivity central nerve to the system entering sure information , nervous of processes high mobility , vehicle apparatus and him supportive autonomous of systems belongs to preparation with depend _ All sports games mixed at speed fast forces with separate stands _ Acyclic actions superiority does _ Purposeful of actions sure execution big important have _ In sports of muscles activity basically is dynamic . However , power technique using muscles significant but short term static stresses develops . This is for sports attraction done of athletes strong preparation serious requirements puts _ In sports games cyclical of actions power variable . Play known at points it is large , submaximal and maximum to be can _ K often game during of an athlete activity short time during is suspended (rules break the ball loss , one minute a break and others) , of power decline and short term stops with recovery processes strengthening need _ They are nerve system of processes high mobility with separate standing qualified in athletes more intensive respectively appear will be Sports games to the body's anaerobic capacity big requirements puts _ If the game very high at pace continue which if (for example , hockey) , anaerobic in the circumstances working the body systems long continue which can't stand stress . This the rules relationship with players to replace permission is given In these sports high to the results reach for anaerobic ability with one aerobic development is also necessary . Sports games variable power their work perform for speed , power , dexterity and special humidity to develop help gives _ Many _ in quantity study downloads common endurance demand for development does _ Sports games with motor skills of those engaged is diverse . Theirs complexity is an athlete on the field fast movement on time the ball take , passes and another game technique to play need _ In sports games , other sports like , tool skills automation Demand will be done .

That 's how much high if so , of an athlete activity so much efficient will be Separately game techniques and even complicated of actions structural parts are also automated to be need _ But the game while playing usual actions ineffective being while remaining such circumstances surface will come Eat it of athletes stereotypical activity created to the circumstances according to change need _ To this conscious respectively and automatic respectively done to be increased extrapolation through is achieved .

With that together , athletes new movement forms which provides new conditional reflexive compounds harvest they do So in sports games stereotypical actions easily change need .This tool activities manager nervous of processes high mobility with is provided . Sports games nervous system of processes mobility improves . Of this indirectly from the indicators one conditional of reflex motor reactions hidden the time is to shorten . With that together , right the answer to choose Demand who does complicated of reactions hidden time is shortened . Hidden of reaction common of time decrease (by 5-20 %) mainly the answer to choose to go of time reduction as a result happen will be Nerve in the system of processes mobility not only movement composition and pace fast change for maybe _ breath get and blood rotation organs is also relevant in the activity changes done increase for is necessary . This bodies their own functions quickly increased going power with increasing and decreasing quickly recovery need _ Game activity fast , agreed and sure actions alb does _ Of this for players and of the ball on the

field location (view and to hear organs by), as well as own of the body status and vestibular and motorized from analyzers come coming out of muscles status about own on time and sure information need _ Sports games support movement devices sure requirements puts _ Players exercises "explosive" strength of muscles , "jumping" endurance, acceleration speed, speed endurance provide need _ The players special strength training skeleton of their ears hypertrophy with together will come But this hypertrophy their speed features not reduce need .

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